

Chevron's Fall And Its Impact On Medical Artificial Intelligence

Sara Gerke (gerke@illinois.edu) & David A. Simon (d.simon@northeastern.edu)

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Excerpt: Because agency rulemaking is now at greater risk of being overruled by courts, *Loper Bright* may increase the FDA's reliance on nonbinding guidance documents to avoid direct legal challenges when regulating medical artificial intelligence and machine learning, but courts could view this as attempting to circumvent the legally binding rulemaking process.

As artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) advances, increasing numbers of manufacturers will incorporate them into medical devices. So far, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has already authorized the marketing of more than [950 AI/ML-enabled devices](#), and the agency is receiving new submissions at a rapid pace. Although the FDA has been actively engaged in addressing new regulatory challenges posed by AI/ML, such as the delineation between [device and non-device software functions](#), most of its actions do not have the official force of law.

Recently, the Supreme Court decided [Loper Bright Enterprises v. Raimondo](#) (2024), which overruled a longstanding legal doctrine that required courts to defer to reasonable agency interpretations of ambiguous statutes. Although theoretically *Loper Bright* directly applies

only to final agency actions that have the official force of law, the decision is likely to have indirect effects on how the FDA regulates medical AI/ML. In this article, we discuss this landmark decision and analyze how it could influence the FDA's approach to regulating medical AI/ML.

The FDA's Current Approach To Medical AI/ML

The FDA has various methods of exercising regulatory authority. One method, [uncommon since 1973](#), is to use formal rulemaking: the agency issues a proposed rule and finalizes it as binding regulation through a process analogous to a judicial proceeding. A second, more common method is informal rulemaking: the agency proposes, take public comments on, and issues a final rule that result in binding regulations. Although federal regulations are legally binding, the rulemaking process is long, governed tightly by the [Administrative Procedure Act](#) (APA), and open to a variety of legal challenges. Partly for these reasons, agencies often seek to act quickly through nonbinding actions, such as issuing discussion papers, guidance documents, and policy statements. While this approach enables the agency to act quickly to project its current thinking on a topic, these materials are *not* legally binding. Nevertheless, nonbinding actions like issuing guidance documents can strongly influence industry behavior.

In developing a framework for AI/ML-enabled devices, the FDA has relied primarily on the latter—nonbinding actions. In 2019, for example, the agency published a [discussion paper](#) proposing a framework for regulating updates to AI/ML-based software as a medical device that relied on a so-called “predetermined change control plan.” Although Congress recently

[gave the FDA express authority](#) (P. L. 117-328, Sec. 3308) to implement its proposal, the agency is constrained by the existing medical device framework, into which medical AI/ML does not fit seamlessly. Additionally, the FDA must address an [exception to the definition of “device”](#) that applies to certain software functions (21 U.S.C. § 360j(o)). Under this exception, the FDA lacks the authority to regulate some clinical decision support software tools because they are *not* considered “devices” under Section 201(h)(1) of the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FDCA).

Since its 2019 discussion paper, the FDA has continued to [develop an innovative approach and published several documents](#) related to AI/ML-enabled devices. However, these actions—such as issuing guidance documents or publishing position papers—communicate the agency’s current view on the topic without legally binding effect. In other words, much of the FDA’s innovative approach is nonbinding; it is *not* based on the rulemaking process, which establishes legally binding federal regulations. As we explain below, *Chevron’s* fall has indirect implications for the stability and legality of the FDA’s evolving approach to regulating AI/ML-enabled devices.

The Supreme Court’s Overruling Of The Chevron Doctrine

Under a longstanding doctrine from [Chevron U.S.A., Inc. v. National Resources Defense Council, Inc.](#) (1984), courts had to defer to reasonable agency interpretations of ambiguous statutes. The Supreme Court in *Loper Bright* recently changed that, overruling *Chevron’s* holding and shifting the balance of interpretive power from agencies to the courts. Instead of deferring to reasonable agency interpretations of ambiguous statutes, courts can now

first ask what power Congress delegated to the agency. If the delegation is broad and sweeping, or specifically called for the agency to “fill up the details” of the statute with regulations, then the reviewing court has to decide only whether the agency action falls within its congressionally delegated authority—an inquiry likely determined by how a court resolves the scope of delegation in the first instance. If not, the court, on its own, decides on the best interpretation of the statute. While the agency’s expertise should not be discounted, *Loper Bright* makes clear that courts are no longer required to defer to it.

Loper Bright has at least two implications. First, it centers the courts, rather than agencies, as the threshold policy maker. Deciding on the proper scope of delegation requires a court to interpret the delegating statute, an exercise that requires understanding the scope and purpose of an agency. Courts may curtail agency actions by narrowing the scope of delegations. Moreover, if the delegation is not clear, then the court can decide for itself what a particular statute means.

Second, because *Loper Bright* applies only to final agency actions (such as regulations), it will likely indirectly affect how agencies exercise their authority. In particular, agencies may rely on more nonbinding exercises of authority, such as through publishing nonbinding guidance documents or position papers. Industry may react to this strategy by increasing litigation or targeting particular nonbinding actions where the FDA’s authority is less certain.

Implications For Medical AI/ML

Loper Bright could indirectly affect the FDA's nimble but mostly nonbinding regulatory approach to AI/ML-enabled devices in several ways. First, it increases uncertainty about the stability of the FDA's approach of relying on nonbinding actions, such as issuing guidance documents and publishing position papers. Although *Loper Bright* does not directly apply to these nonbinding actions, it suggests courts will treat them with even greater skepticism. In particular, courts may increasingly find that agencies like the FDA use nonbinding actions like issuing guidance documents to circumvent the rulemaking process. In such cases, courts may hold that nonbinding actions constitute final agency actions subject to review under *Loper Bright*.

Even before *Loper Bright*, courts were sometimes suspicious of nonbinding agency exercises of authority. For example, in [*Appalachian Power Co. v. Environmental Protection Agency*](#) (EPA) (D.C. Cir. 2000), the United States Court of Appeals for the District of Columbia Circuit struck down an EPA guidance because it unlawfully expanded the scope of federal regulations. The court pointed out that with the use of a guidance document, EPA tried to “immuniz[e] its lawmaking from judicial review” because “it is not final, and it is not final because it is not ‘binding.’” However, the court clarified that it was a de-facto rule since “[i]t commands, it requires, it orders, it dictates” and “it should have been, but was not, promulgated in compliance with notice and comment rulemaking procedures.” Courts may rely on this line of jurisprudence when faced with an agency that is reluctant to use rulemaking but eager to take informal actions to influence the behavior of regulated parties.

At a minimum, these cases suggest that courts are paying attention to agency attempts to use guidance documents to evade judicial review. This approach could gain additional support if agencies avoid rulemaking and rely instead on nonbinding actions.

Uncertainty about how courts will decide cases after *Chevron's* fall and how the FDA will proceed in light of it may also cause firms to take a “wait and see” approach to novel product development, potentially hampering innovation. Consider the following example concerning AI/ML: 21 U.S.C. § 360j(o)(1)(E) exempts from the definition of a “device” certain clinical decision support software functions, including those that enable a “health care professional [HCP] to independently review the basis for . . . [the software’s] recommendations” In a [guidance document](#), [the FDA has interpreted these ambiguous words](#) to include only certain *types* of “independent review.” For example, [the FDA excludes](#) those “software functions intended for a critical, time-sensitive task or decision . . . , because an HCP is unlikely to have sufficient time to independently review the basis of the recommendations.”

Under a strict reading of the APA, neither *Chevron* nor *Loper Bright* would apply to this guidance document because it fails to qualify as a legally binding “final agency action” under the APA ([5 U.S.C. § 704](#)). If courts choose this approach, they may view this guidance document as irrelevant and discard it summarily. Indeed, *Loper Bright* generally suggests that courts are more likely than ever to dismiss the FDA’s nonbinding interpretations and purported policy objectives. On the other hand, decisions like *Appalachian Power Co.* suggest that some courts may treat certain guidance documents as final agency actions

subject to judicial review. As a result, companies thinking about investing in this area of technology may be reluctant to do so if the FDA's position is subject to the increased risk of being challenged in a lawsuit and eventually rejected by a court.

Second, and somewhat paradoxically, *Loper Bright* may incentivize the FDA to increase its reliance on guidance documents. From a resource perspective, nonbinding actions are less time-consuming than agency rulemaking. From a risk perspective, *Loper Bright* makes it more likely that a court may overrule the FDA's interpretation when arrived at through rulemaking. While courts may treat some nonbinding actions like issuing guidance documents as final agency actions subject to court review, at least some nonbinding actions will not be reviewable even under *Loper Bright*. From the FDA's perspective, then, it may be cheaper, quicker, and no less risky to use nonbinding actions to accomplish policy goals that, under *Chevron*, may have been pursued through the rulemaking process. However, increased use of nonbinding actions may invite judicial scrutiny, and could persuade courts to begin treating guidance documents as final agency actions subject to judicial review under *Loper Bright*. All of these factors increase regulatory uncertainty and instability.

Third, if the FDA continues to exercise authority through nonbinding actions, it is likely that adversely affected firms will mount more frequent and bold challenges to them. Conversely, if firms view the FDA's nonbinding actions favorably, it may be more difficult to motivate the FDA to undergo a legally binding rulemaking process that could be subject to challenge. Since challenges are more likely to be successful and industry is unlikely to challenge favorable nonbinding actions, a possible industry-friendly default may result.

Fourth, and somewhat more optimistically, *Loper Bright* may force Congress to specifically provide the FDA with new authority to regulate AI/ML. However, it is unclear whether and when this will happen. It may take extensive litigation—both about the FDA’s authority and about liability for injuries resulting from AI/ML-enabled medical products—to spur Congress to action.

The Future Regulatory Landscape Of Medical AI/ML

The current regulatory landscape of medical AI/ML is already complex, fragmented, and opaque. On the one hand, *Loper Bright* may exacerbate these problems, perhaps by incentivizing the FDA to continue using nonbinding actions to adapt to a new regulatory environment. On the other hand, *Loper Bright* could spur overdue congressional action on AI/ML-enabled devices, charting a clear regulatory pathway for the FDA. For example, it would be helpful for Congress to bring all clinical decision support software under the device framework. [If done correctly](#), this could eliminate the need for the FDA to creatively interpret the federal device law to effectively regulate risky products, such as AI algorithms intended to detect sepsis and alert the HCP. Direct regulation could also improve innovation and patient safety by preventing unsafe or ineffective products from reaching the market.

However, even a congressional delegation of specific powers to the FDA would raise additional regulatory concerns. In general, the FDA’s binding interpretations of legislation in regulations are likely to see an increasing number of legal challenges, with industry feeling bolstered by *Loper Bright*. Even the most specific legislation cannot anticipate the

myriad linguistic issues likely to arise in long-term regulation of an evolving and technical landscape like medical AI/ML. And while Congress can try to avoid judicial meddling in agency affairs by making broad delegations of authority to the FDA, directing it to “fill up the details” of the statute, *Loper Bright* may undercut such delegations because it still requires courts to assess the scope of delegation and whether the agency action falls within it. In short, the case moves the locus of policy-making from the agency to the courts—the agencies are no longer considered the exclusive experts on matters of interpretation.

Loper Bright is a landmark decision that likely has considerable implications for how the FDA exercises its regulatory authority. Because agency rulemaking is now at greater risk of being overruled by courts, *Loper Bright* may increase the FDA’s reliance on guidance documents to avoid direct legal challenges when regulating medical AI/ML. This, however, could backfire: [courts might view the FDA’s increased reliance on nonbinding actions as attempting to circumvent the binding rulemaking process](#), especially in a novel and evolving area like AI/ML. In effect, courts may find nonbinding guidance documents in areas like AI/ML to constitute final agency action subject to judicial review under *Loper Bright*. Policymakers and stakeholders like developers, physicians, and hospitals should watch developments closely to understand their potential impact on the regulation of medical AI/ML.

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Author Bios

Sara Gerke is an Associate Professor of Law and Richard W. & Marie L. Corman Scholar at the College of Law, as well as an Associate Professor at the European Union Center, at the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign. Her research focuses on the ethical and legal challenges of artificial intelligence and big data for health care and health law in the United States and Europe. Professor Gerke is leading several research projects funded by the NIH and the European Union. She has over 60 publications in health law and bioethics, especially AI and digital health. Her work has appeared in leading law, medical, scientific, and bioethics journals, such as *The George Washington Law Review*, *Yale Journal of Health Policy, Law, and Ethics*, *JAMA*, *Science*, *Nature Medicine*, *npj Digital Medicine*, *Nature*

Machine Intelligence, Nature Biotechnology, The Lancet Digital Health, Journal of Law and the Biosciences, Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics, Hastings Center Report, and The American Journal of Bioethics, as well as books published by Cambridge University Press, Elsevier, and Springer. Before joining UIUC, Professor Gerke was an Assistant Professor of Law at Penn State Dickinson Law and was promoted early to Associate Professor of Law in 2024. Before that, she served as a Research Fellow in Medicine, Artificial Intelligence, and Law at the Petrie-Flom Center for Health Law Policy, Biotechnology, and Bioethics at Harvard Law School for the Project on Precision Medicine, Artificial Intelligence, and the Law (PMAIL).

David A. Simon is an Associate Professor of Law at Northeastern University School of Law, where he is core faculty at the Center for Health Policy & Law (CHPL) and the Center for Law, Information & Creativity (CLIC). He is also a co-director of the Amy J. Reed Collaborative on Device Safety, funded by Arnold Ventures and a member of the research team at CLASSICA, a major research project on AI-assisted cancer surgery funded by the European Union. Dr. Simon previously has been a faculty member at Harvard Law School, George Washington University Law School, and the University of Kansas School of Law. His scholarship--which focuses on health, intellectual property, innovation, and tort law--has appeared or will appear in a variety of legal publications, including the Texas Law Review, the Northwestern Law Review, the Boston College Law Review, the Emory Law Journal, the Georgia Law Review, the Florida Law Review, the Journal of the American Medical Association, the Journal of Law & the Biosciences, the Oxford Journal of Legal Studies, the

Washington Law Review, the Wisconsin Law Review, the William & Mary Law Review, the Yale Journal of Law & the Humanities, and the Yale Journal of Law & Technology.